

Nintendo and the Evolution of Video Game Consoles

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Good morning, readers. Today, we will discuss gaming systems. I will talk about the role of the company Nintendo in the history of home consoles, which over the last forty years has aimed to establish itself as a market leader in the video game industry, while also betting on innovation.

Although Nintendo was by no means the company that originated the concept of the home console or video games—or many other related ideas—it has been the company that best understood the market and made these systems popular.

Nintendo in the Second Generation of Video Game Console

The first home video game console in history was the Magnavox Odyssey, conceived and created by the renowned Ralph Henry Baer in the 1940s, and released on the market in 1972. It was followed by other well-known consoles produced by Coleco, Mattel, and, above all, Atari.

However, Nintendo was not that present in the first generation of video game consoles, fully joining the so-called "second generation"—which coincided with the “Golden Age” of arcade machines and arcades, as well as the video game market crash in the United States. At that time, the then-not-so-giant Kyoto-based company had just entered the video game market, and its first consoles were the Color TV-Game systems—sold between 1977 and 1980, thus, being part of the first generation of video game consoles.

Unlike some other companies, which were already developing storage media required to run certain games on a system, Nintendo initially stuck to producing dedicated consoles—systems in which the games were built into the console’s memory rather than stored on external media—before later adopting this alternative approach.

Nintendo would not be the only company to continue releasing dedicated consoles; for example, various Magnavox models also followed this approach. By then, different companies were already considering the international market, not just the national one. Despite not being that innovative, the different Color TV-Game models were a success, selling several million units, which helped Nintendo to take the video game market seriously and pursue future projects on a much larger scale.

Left: players using the original 1972 Magnavox Odyssey. Right: a Japanese family playing with the Color TV-Game 112 Racing model.

NES and the Leap to International Fame

Hiroshi Yamauchi, then president of Nintendo —and descendant of the company’s founder—, almost certainly observing the financial crisis in the video game sector in the early 1980s in the United States, decided that the time had come for Nintendo to fully enter the American market —and, consequently, later the global market. In 1983, Nintendo released its first home console with external storage media —cartridges—, the Famicom (Family Computer), which was becoming a success in Japan.

The momentum that the Famicom had given the company in Japan in 1983 was the trigger that led Nintendo to redesign the console as the NES (Nintendo Entertainment System) and release it under that name internationally. NES arrived at the perfect moment for Nintendo, as during the first-generation crisis —when users were shifting from home consoles to arcades and personal computers— it managed to reignite public interest in home video games.

Taking advantage of the new technology available at the time, such as low cost microprocessors, NES offered colourful, highly detailed graphics compared to what Atari and other companies had provided before their decline; games with a friendly appearance designed to appeal to the whole family, such as *Duck Hunt*, *Mega Man*, and *Super Mario* itself... and also for older audiences, such as *Metroid* and *Castlevania*. Nintendo took the original idea of Mr. Baer —bringing players together with their families at home to play video games— and continued it; even the NES included shooting game controllers inspired by those created by Baer years earlier.

The NES designer —and later also of the Super Famicom—, Masayuki Uemura, also incorporated the control devised by Gunpei Yokoi: the famous “D-pad,” which has been used in one form or another by virtually every console manufacturer ever since. It was originally developed for the Game & Watch designed by Yokoi, specifically for the Donkey Kong model from 1982.

The Donkey Kong Game & Watch model, showing the D-pad controller, and to its right, the original 1983 Nintendo Famicom, which also featured this directional control

The Origin of Nintendo’s Handhelds

The Game & Watch systems, in turn, represented Nintendo’s first foray into the handheld console market. Conceived by Yokoi while traveling on the Shinkansen — Japanese bullet train—, he saw a man fiddling with his calculator and thought that small systems could be created using similar technology, allowing gamers to play during their trips.

Yokoi had the idea to create small dedicated systems that used the LCD display technology of calculators and digital watches, which was low-power, and included simple yet fun games.

While Nintendo was not the pioneer in creating handheld consoles—credit goes to the toy company Mattel, which made its dedicated gaming systems starting in 1976 with Mattel Electronics Auto Race—they were the manufacturer that best popularized this form of play. Milton Bradley also produced dedicated handheld systems, but stood out as the pioneer in creating a portable console that used cartridges—external storage systems—to allow players to play different games.

Thus, Milton Bradley’s Microvision was released in 1979. This console suffered from drawbacks such as an excessively small screen and a control and display system that wore down too quickly with use. Moreover, the cartridges would eventually fail due to their electronic contacts and the way they interfaced with the game’s control system.

It would take ten years for Nintendo to release a portable system that would literally “sweep” the market of any competition. Atari, Sega, Mattel... all released handheld consoles, but it was Nintendo’s 1989 Game Boy, once again designed by Mr. Yokoi, that dominated the market almost entirely for twenty years.

The Game Boy may not have been the most powerful portable gaming device—relying on black and white graphics, or rather “green” and black— but it had advantages that made it the undisputed market leader.

Robustly designed with high-quality materials—there is a known case of a Game Boy that still works after surviving an explosion in the Gulf War; and my own 1990 Game Boy, having suffered all kinds of misadventures, still functions perfectly while I write this article—it also offered a battery life and autonomy that no competitor could match.

With four AA batteries, depending on their quality, the Game Boy could run for around forty hours, while its more powerful competitors, like Sega’s Game Gear, offered only three or four hours using not four, but up to six batteries.

Atari, with its Lynx, which also technically surpassed the Game Boy and even offered backlighting—like the Game Gear—would suffer the same fate as Sega’s handhelds and other brands when competing against the Game Boy, since it suffered from the same issues as Sega’s Game Gear and other handhelds of the era. Add to this that the Game Boy, despite being quite large, was more manageable than its competitors.

On top of all this, we must add Nintendo’s dedication to constantly supporting its handheld with high-quality games for years. The Game Boy gave birth to franchises like Kirby and Pokémon, and even offered a portable version of The Legend of Zelda, *Link’s Awakening*, in 1993—though the later “Oracle” titles, Oracle of Ages and Oracle of Seasons, with their good length and high quality, and exclusive to the later Game Boy Color, would be the true portable ambassadors of Zelda for years.

Microvision console by Milton Bradley, and a Game Boy exhibited at the V&A Museum of Childhood, London

Nintendo during the 16-bit Era: The “War” with Sega

Sega was Nintendo’s main competitor at the time, a company that had built its own reputation largely thanks to its commendable work in the arcade sector. Sega had released its own 8-bit home console, the Mark III or Master System, in 1986—by which point the NES was already well established, making it harder for Sega to gain significant market penetration—but still achieved a notable market share.

It was a solid gaming system that enjoyed moderate success in Europe, Brazil, and other countries, but it was completely overshadowed by Nintendo in Japan and the United States. Sega sought to get ahead of Nintendo with its next release, the Sega Mega Drive (known as the “Genesis” in the U.S. and other regions).

In 1988, Sega made a strong impression with this console, which offered high power and speed, featuring one of the best arcade ports ever: *Altered Beast*, perfectly adapted for a home system. A few years later, the company introduced the first game starring its new mascot, the hedgehog Sonic, challenging players with high-speed scrolling and delivering a sense of frenetic action never seen before in a platformer.

Nintendo did not want to fall behind a console that boasted high-quality arcade titles and released its own system, the Super Famicom (Super Nintendo Entertainment System in the West, also known as “Super NES” or “SNES”) in 1990. With an aggressive marketing campaign—ensuring continued cooperation with major third-party companies to provide games for the console—and by launching new titles for its already well-known franchises, Nintendo consolidated its position.

During this period, new game series that remain beloved today, such as F-Zero and Star Fox, also emerged.

Nintendo was fully established and secure in the console business at this stage, but competition with Sega and NEC Computers encouraged it to maintain strong efforts in the sector. For instance, up until that time, Nintendo applied strict censorship to avoid excessive violence in games for its systems. However, the controversy over the graphic violence in titles such as *Mortal Kombat*, which went uncensored on Sega’s Mega Drive—since Sega targeted teenage and adult audiences with such games—led to the creation of systems such as the ESRB. The ESRB continues to classify video games by age and content today, making strict censorship less necessary, though some restrictions remain for specific titles and in certain countries.

This period is known as the “First Console War,” a more or less healthy competition between Sega and Nintendo, as well as between their fanbases defending their preferred home gaming system. This rivalry would continue between these companies and future competitors for Mario, Sonic, and others. Of course, other companies existed—such as SNK with its Neo Geo, released in 1990, a very powerful system whose high price, both for the console and its cartridges, prevented it from competing on equal terms with Sega or Nintendo.

Meanwhile, in the portable market, Nintendo continued to dominate thanks to the Game Boy. Sega and other companies failed to dethrone it—Sega even released the Sega Nomad in 1995 for the U.S. market, essentially a portable Mega Drive, impressive in power for a handheld at that time. Yokoi made design improvements to the Game Boy, including the smaller Game Boy Pocket, which required only two batteries instead of four, further cementing its dominance in the portable market.

European version of the Sega Mega Drive, and the Japanese version of the Super Nintendo: Super Famicom

The 32- and 64-Bit Consoles Era and the Emergence of a New Rival

The Super NES was still holding strong in 1994, when the celebrated original *Donkey Kong Country*—from the company Rare—was released, selling over six million units during the console’s final life cycle.

At a time when competitors were already opting for more powerful systems, Nintendo had not yet taken the next step—although both Sega and Nintendo were working hard to release peripherals that added extra capabilities to their consoles, such as the Super Game Boy or the Sega Mega-CD.

And then something unexpected happened. Just as Nintendo seemed poised to take the next leap, it was in the midst of designing its next console that it was collaborating with Sony, the popular electronics company, to incorporate an optical drive into its future system—originally planned to be called the “Nintendo PlayStation”—to allow it to read CDs. This would enable greater storage capacity, higher-quality audio tracks, and the inclusion of video sequences and voice acting in games.

However, the negotiations ultimately fell through, as Nintendo was not satisfied with the allegedly abusive terms Sony wanted to impose—and vice versa. The agreement was broken, and Sony, undeterred, decided to enter the console market itself, creating what would become the renowned Sony PlayStation in 1994, which brought us so many iconic titles.

A similar situation occurred with Hudson. Not interested in the technology Hudson offered at the end of the NES life cycle, the company partnered with NEC to release other consoles that could compete in the market years before the Sony issue arose.

Several third-party companies, such as Konami and Square Enix, shifted their focus to Sony's new console —having previously developed mainly for Nintendo and Sega— drawn by the potential of CD technology, even though the Sega Mega-CD already enabled its use with the Sega Mega Drive. Meanwhile, Nintendo suffered a major setback with the release of the Virtual Boy in 1995, which was an outright failure.

Nintendo opted to innovate in gameplay and provide a machine with respectable power to deliver technically impressive games. Despite the limitations imposed by the absence of an optical drive, the Nintendo 64 —released in 1996 and named after its 64-bit processor— was the last Nintendo home console to use classic cartridges as its primary storage medium, if we exclude the use of memory cards and cartridge-based systems in portable consoles, such as the Game Boy line, and modern consoles like the Nintendo Switch and its successor, Switch 2. Nintendo compensated with peripherals such as the Rumble Pak, which added vibration functionality to the controller and enhanced gameplay in certain titles.

Fortunately, despite the lack of real recorded cinematic sequences or soundtracks beyond synthesised music, Nintendo and its developers continued delivering true masterpieces, including *Super Mario 64*, *The Legend of Zelda: Ocarina of Time* and *Majora's Mask*, *Star Fox 64*, *GoldenEye*, and the first *Pikmin* —the latter only released in Japan.

Sega, with the Sega Saturn —a competent console that nevertheless failed to gain traction against the PlayStation and the still-respected Nintendo— and Nintendo itself, could not overcome Sony, which offered a console that was easy to program for (and, unfortunately, easy to pirate —a factor that ultimately helped Sony sell consoles at unprecedented rates), affordable for consumers, and backed by an already massive game library.

In the portable arena, Nintendo released the Game Boy Color in 1998, offering greater power than previous Game Boy systems and, as its name indicated, finally providing a colour display for a Nintendo handheld. SNK released the Neo Geo Pocket the same year, but quickly phased it out in favour of a colour version in 1999.

For SNK and other Nintendo competitors, however, Kyoto's giant had an unbeatable ace: the franchise considered the most important in handheld console history: Pokémon —still a major franchise today—, which drove Nintendo hardware sales at a remarkable pace. For the Game Boy Color in 1999, its second generation launched in two editions —Gold and Silver— followed by a third, Crystal. Moreover, this release was backward compatible with the original 1989 Game Boy —making the Game Boy Color even more popular. Titles like Pokémon Crystal, however, were not compatible with the original Game Boy or the Game Boy Pocket.

Here we see part of the Nintendo 64's presence in popular culture —despite not outselling its competitors, it has enjoyed enormous fame and affection among video game enthusiasts and console collectors—. On the left, Josuke Higashikata, protagonist of the fourth story arc of *JoJo's Bizarre Adventure*, with his Nintendo 64 console (in the manga he actually owns a Super Famicom). The image corresponds to the animated version, released in 2016. On the right, a screenshot of *Final Fantasy VII* for PC. This game was one of the jewels that, due to Nintendo abandoning CD support and losing collaboration with Sony —which went on to create its own console— did not appear on a Nintendo system until several years after, being ported for the Nintendo Switch.

Nintendo and the Sixth Generation: Console “Wars” Return

With the Nintendo GameCube, Nintendo finally moved into the territory of consoles with optical media support. By now, a new competitor had joined Sony in the market: Microsoft, with its Xbox, boasting superior power and backed by a key player in computing, Mr Gates. This meant Nintendo had to really push itself like never before.

This generation marked a graphical leap from the previous one, and consoles now offered DVD compatibility, flash memory alongside traditional hard drives, and the early rise of online gaming.

For this console generation, Nintendo focused on consolidating its most famous franchises, while also betting on third-party companies such as Capcom, which released several exclusives with the support of figures like Shinji Mikami, including a certain Resident Evil title —*Resident Evil 4*, which would later become less exclusive.

Critics from various media outlets argued that Nintendo was neglecting the more serious, adult audience, and Nintendo responded with a console that offered power, third-party support, and a wide variety of games to appeal to adults as well. Action, RPG, horror, sports, platformers, shooters —there was something for everyone.

Despite the quality of the GameCube —and the excellence of systems like Sega's Dreamcast— Sony had firmly established itself in the console market; and the success of the PlayStation continued with its successor, the PlayStation 2, released in 2000, which boasted such an avalanche of diverse titles and fame that it became the best-selling video game system of its generation and of all time. The GameCube was also disadvantaged by the fact that the PlayStation 2 could play standard DVDs, while the GameCube relied on Nintendo's own optical discs, and by being one of the last consoles to launch in that generation, long after Sony had already secured its market position.

On the other hand, Microsoft's Xbox achieved significant success thanks to several factors: its high power, inclusion of a hard drive —useful for saving games and updates, for example—, the ability for developers to use PC programming tools —making development easier—, and its online service, which continues today with its successors, Xbox One and the Series consoles via Xbox Live. It should be noted that consoles such as the PlayStation and PlayStation 2 relied on external memory cards to store player data —game saves, etc.—.

This was a generation of consoles that gave rise to the three “factions”: the three most popular companies to this day, effectively overshadowing the rest of the market and continuing to compete at present.

These factions were Nintendo, Sony, and Microsoft —unfortunately, Sega, after the disaster of the Dreamcast, despite releasing true masterpieces for it such as the two Shenmue games, decided to withdraw as a console manufacturer, if we don't take the Sega Mega Drive mini consoles into account—, and they continue “battling” today with their current consoles, striving to outsell the others —the Dreamcast sold over ten million units, less than half of its immediate competitor, the GameCube.

In the portable sector, Nintendo released the Game Boy Advance in 2001, a hugely successful handheld console that delivered one of the most extensive game libraries —around 1538 licensed titles— in video game history, including an exceptionally high number of top-quality titles.

The original version of this console featured a large screen and backward compatibility with Game Boy Color and original Game Boy games —including Game Boy Pocket—. Later, there was a smaller version, the Game Boy Micro, which ran only Game Boy Advance titles; and another version with a backlit screen (depending on the model) and rechargeable battery —a major improvement over constantly buying external batteries or “cells”—, the Game Boy Advance SP.

While other handheld consoles existed, such as Bandai's WonderSwan from 1999, designed by Gunpei Yokoi after leaving Nintendo, its later colour revision in 2000, and the Crystal version in 2002, none provided real competition for Nintendo in the portable market, let alone internationally. Bandai did not even target markets outside Japan. As for other companies, systems like Nokia's N-Gage mobile consoles achieved some recognition, but Nintendo still maintained its near-monopoly over the handheld market.

Left: special edition Game Boy Micro running the *Pokémon Emerald* game. Right: Game Boy Advance SP.

Nintendo Wii and the Revolution in Control

The seventh generation of video game consoles would be known for the inclusion of new optical and video formats: Blu-Ray, HD DVD; and for the full rise of online gaming communities. Hiroshi Yamauchi passed the baton of Nintendo's presidency—renouncing his pension, citing that the company could make better use of those funds, in a display of respect and trust towards his colleagues—to Satoru Iwata, one of the company's most notable employees and an experienced programmer behind classics such as *Balloon Fight* (1984).

Yamauchi continued to work at Nintendo for a while, but felt he could retire knowing he could fully trust Iwata's work as the company's top executive.

A close friend of Shigeru Miyamoto since youth—they have always admired each other—Iwata also contributed to well-known franchises by Nintendo and HAL Laboratory, such as Kirby and EarthBound, and later collaborated on the Super Smash Bros and Pokémon series.

It is worth noting that, despite being president and the most important figure at Nintendo, Iwata continued to roll up his sleeves and work alongside programming teams as one of them: writing and debugging code, giving ideas to his colleagues—even correcting bugs and assisting Masahiro Sakurai's team in balancing character stats and abilities in Smash Bros titles.

Iwata and his team conceived the Nintendo Wii, the first home console since the NES and Super NES that emphasised family use, enhanced by the motion-control system and the peripherals created for it. While not the first console to employ such technology, it was the first to place such emphasis on it and become a remarkable commercial success. The Wii competed with the Xbox 360—the first console released in this generation, in 2005—and the PlayStation 3, both offering HDMI support (high-definition video) and superior power compared to the Wii.

The console market landscape inspired Iwata to conceive the Wii and to abandon competing solely on raw performance and features—a largely futile contest, given the invincible PC in those areas—in favour of new directions.

Iwata believed that Nintendo's previous strategy—which had failed in two console generations—of emphasising graphical power and focusing on the more traditional, hardcore gaming audience needed expanding. Thus, he dedicated himself to creating a home system that innovated in control—although the Wii still offered the option to play with a classic controller for most titles—while attracting a broader audience.

Nintendo succeeded in outperforming competitors with these strategies, and the Wii became the best-selling console of that generation. Although it might seem that Nintendo focused exclusively on family-friendly or “infantile” experiences and mostly simple gameplay, this would be a mistake.

The console's marketing and target audience did not define its entire catalogue: the Wii offered ambitious and high-quality games such as *Xenoblade Chronicles* —now available for New 3DS in portable format, and for Nintendo Switch and Switch 2—, *MadWorld*, *The Legend of Zelda: Twilight Princess* and *Skyward Sword*, *Fire Emblem: Radiant Dawn*, *Metroid Prime III: Corruption* —also available in a compilation with the two previous Metroid Prime games for GameCube—, the two excellent Super Mario Galaxy titles, and more.

The Wii also featured the Virtual Console service, an online platform allowing the purchase of games from a multitude of classic consoles —including Atari systems, Commodore computers, and classic arcade machines.

The Emergence of Real Competition in the Portable Market

Nintendo released the Nintendo DS in 2004, a handheld console based on a dual-screen design, reminiscent of the Game & Watch *Donkey Kong 2* (1983), designed by the late Gunpei Yokoi.

The DS's lower screen was touch-sensitive, enabling the use of emerging technology —which was beginning to gain popularity at the time and is now ubiquitous in mobile devices— to provide new gameplay controls. The DS also featured a microphone and a wireless device for online connectivity, while later models added a camera.

By then, Sony had already become a home console giant and decided it was time to challenge Nintendo directly in the handheld console market.

In 2004, the Tokyo-based company released the PlayStation Portable (PSP), a high-quality handheld console with several notable titles. It even received its own canonical Metal Gear entry —*Metal Gear Solid: Peace Walker*— and two God of War titles, as well as classic remakes or remasters like *Tactics Ogre: Let Us Cling Together* and *Valkyrie Profile: Lenneth*, all of exceptional quality. While it did not defeat Nintendo as market leader, it did pose a serious challenge to the creators of Mario and the like.

On the left, an elderly person playing with the Nintendo Wii —in some medical centres, this console has even been used in rehabilitation therapy—. On the right, young Japanese commuters in the metro with Nintendo and Sony handheld consoles —a PSP on the left and two DS units to the right—.

In this generation, moreover, mobile phone and computing companies such as Apple were also trying to enter the video game market, taking advantage of the ever-increasing power and affordability of high-performance mobile devices —something that would later pose a real threat to traditional consoles.

The eighth generation: the rise of mobile gaming and the battle for Virtual Reality, “4K”, and raw power

What characterised the eighth generation of consoles —which began in November 2012 with Nintendo’s release of the Wii U— was the intense and aggressive competition brought about by the boom in the smartphone market, and by the ultimately futile attempts of video game companies Sony and Microsoft to match consoles with personal computers in terms of raw power and capabilities.

This reached such a level that upgraded versions of their consoles were released, offering greater power than the original models, and 4K output —even if it was merely upscaled, since it was completely impossible for consoles with such limited hardware, compared to a mid- or high-range PC of the time, to display native 4K resolution at a much lower price than a PC or Mac. This generation was also marked by a race to offer greater integration of services beyond gaming itself —arguably the most attractive and innovative aspect of this generation, which continues into the ninth generation alongside the trends mentioned above.

For example, Sony introduced Virtual Reality technology through headsets designed specifically for the PlayStation 4 —a console whose original model was released in 2013. What was particularly interesting about this generation was the way manufacturers innovated with their systems to provide new possibilities, such as recording and sharing gameplay footage, and integration with online services like Twitch. The PlayStation 4 also added a motion control device and a small touch panel to its classic controller.

Meanwhile, Microsoft’s Xbox One, released in 2013, also allowed users to record and share gameplay videos online and functions as a multitasking system, making it possible to use the console in a way slightly more similar to a PC —for instance, a game can be paused to browse the internet or access other applications such as Skype or the Microsoft Store.

As it was previously stated, Nintendo’s contribution to this console generation was the Wii U. The Wii U featured a controller/tablet —or “GamePad”— which allowed users to either turn off the TV (or have someone else watch it in their place) and continue playing on the controller, or use it as a screen for the console without a television.

It could also be used for new control methods and augmented reality or visualisation functions —for example, checking the map of a game level, or the character’s inventory in certain games. The console was also compatible with Wii peripherals such as the motion-sensing controller, the Wiimote, and the Wii MotionPlus.

However, the console failed to generate real interest among the public. The Wii U launched with considerably lower power than the forthcoming Xbox One and PlayStation 4—closer to that of its predecessors—and, presumably due to the higher cost of incorporating the tablet controller, was priced too close to these more powerful systems. Its limited catalogue—which was later largely re-released on the Nintendo Switch—in comparison with other consoles (the original Wii, PlayStation 4, and Xbox One), meant it received little support from third-party developers and failed to attract a significant audience.

In the handheld market, Nintendo was far more successful, despite a difficult start in this generation. They released the Nintendo 3DS in 2011, the first console to offer stereoscopic 3D without the need for specialised glasses—a feature that was significantly improved in later models, the New Nintendo 3DS and New Nintendo 3DS XL, which also added a second analogue stick to facilitate control in many games.

Meanwhile, Sony launched the PlayStation Vita, the most powerful handheld console to that date.

On the left, the original 3DS model from 2011 running *Pilotwings Resort*. On the right, an image showing the PlayStation Vita being used as a controller—and display for remote play—for the PlayStation 4.

Both consoles offer touch controls, although the PlayStation Vita has a single—touch—screen, albeit of higher resolution and visual quality, while the 3DS featured two smaller screens—one being touch-sensitive and the other capable of displaying stereoscopic 3D content. The Vita utilises a rear touch panel to add functionality to the system’s physical buttons.

The original Vita screen was made with OLED technology, offering superior colour accuracy, contrast, and overall display quality compared to LCD. Unfortunately, Sony ceased using OLED in later Vita models to reduce costs, so if you wish to own one of those OLED models, it is advisable not to wait too long as their value on the second-hand market is been rising since that moment.

Sony gradually withdrew support for the PlayStation Vita after its launch—a real shame given the system’s exceptional quality and the many outstanding games released for it, such as *Soul Sacrifice*, *Gravity Rush*, *Dragon’s Crown*, *Uncharted: Golden Abyss*, *Persona 4: The Golden*—a superb RPG originally for PlayStation 2—and two previous Ninja Gaiden entries for the Xbox and Xbox 360 ported to this system.

Sony's and Microsoft's interest in stereoscopic 3D was also hinted at along these years—as it had been for motion controls with peripherals such as Sony's EyeToy and Move, or Microsoft's Kinect—, but in Sony's case it was focused on the PlayStation 3 instead of releasing an updated Vita with a 3D-compatible screen. The PS3 later allowed 3D video playback, although this depended on the TV and its 3D capabilities.

Nintendo, despite a difficult start with the 3DS—including a price drop shortly after launch and a giveaway of classic games to early buyers to boost sales— managed to recover, with the console eventually enjoying a vast and high-quality library.

Although 3DS was far less powerful and graphically capable than the Vita, it still delivered true gems such as *Bravely Default* and *Bravely Second: End Layer*, the new Monster Hunter entries and/or ports —*3 Ultimate*, *4 Ultimate*, and *Generations*, the latter later released on Switch in an enhanced version—, *Resident Evil: Revelations* (which was subsequently released on other platforms), and the remakes of *Ocarina of Time* and *Majora's Mask*. At the time of writing this article, Pokémon Sun and Moon were already available on the system.

While writing, I regretted having to pause the magnificent and nearly endless *Dragon Quest VII*, released as a remake for this console. It is worth noting that *Dragon Quest VIII* was also being prepared for 3DS while I wrote this article, and that *Dragon Quest VII* would later receive a remake for Nintendo Switch in 2026, titled *Dragon Quest VII: Reimagined*.

As the tone of this article indicates, one of the main takeaways from this generation and the next is the ongoing drive to displace the personal computer as the premier gaming platform and to target users simply for choosing a different system. Microsoft's decision to scale back its console focus in the 2020s demonstrates the futility of these efforts, at a time when more and more console-exclusive titles are also released on PC or Mac—clear examples being *God of War* (2018), its sequel *Ragnarök* (2022), and *Helldivers 2* (2024), all developed by studios funded and/or published by Sony.

Today, it is indisputable that the PC is the most suitable platform for home gaming—both in terms of system and game prices (a PC is often more expensive than a console, especially a Mac, but the investment pays off), as well as utility and convenience for gaming.

Do you prefer playing with a controller? No problem—simply connect it to your PC as you would with a console and start playing. Free online modes are available, and if you usually play with a PS4 or PS5 connected to a TV, it's just as convenient to open a 17-inch laptop and start playing *Dark Souls III* or *Elden Ring* within seconds, using a controller, with the ability to record gameplay, take screenshots, suspend the game, and resume work or check emails—all on the same device. It's a matter of personal preference, as comfortable as console gaming can also be.

Thirty or twenty years ago, such criticisms were understandable; gaming on a PC or Mac was far more cumbersome, expensive, and inconvenient. But with modern advances, falling prices, and platforms like Steam offering free online services and excellent user support, such complaints are now entirely unfounded.

Companies have preferred to compete by releasing increasingly powerful console models, even though it is ironically criticised that PCs require upgrades over time. Nintendo itself has fallen into this habit, releasing improved console versions, such as the New 3DS in 2015.

If previous console generations emphasised frequent HD revisions or remasters of classic and recent games, this trend continues today with titles such as *The Last of Us*, *The Elder Scrolls V: Skyrim*, or the aforementioned *Dragon Quest VII: Reimagined*.

It is also worth noting the tactics used to secure console exclusives, often blocking or downgrading PC versions to prevent sales —*Assassin's Creed*, I'm looking at you. Moreover, attempts to disparage PC gamers to encourage switching to consoles — primarily by Sony, while Microsoft, as the developer of the most popular PC operating system, has been more cautious— also continue, just as some PC gamers constantly criticise console players.

In short, this is a polarisation that has affected the gaming world in recent years.

Nintendo has been smart in exploring alternative platforms, releasing *Pokémon Go* last decade, which became a massive success via Niantic on mobile devices. Apple also hosted a Mario title on its devices: *Super Mario Run*.

After the success of Nintendo Wii, Iwata urged his team not to rest on their laurels. Despite poor market decisions —such as the mishandling of Wii U, or the overuse of DLCs in games like *Smash Bros Wii U*, *Mario Kart 8*, and *Mario Kart World* for Switch and Switch 2— Nintendo took calculated risks.

The heavy emphasis on Amiibo figures also offered limited benefit beyond financial gains and the speculative market —although some were re-released, exclusive models contributed to price increases.

Of all decisions in the last decade, Nintendo made one particularly bold and commendable choice, which I will discuss next. Yes, Nintendo has stumbled, but it did so by taking risks. Sega and Atari also took risks and lost —though Sega still thrives as a distributor, behind masterpieces like *Alien: Isolation* and the Total War strategy series by The Creative Assembly, and in the collectibles market—, but at least they attempted daring ideas, sometimes delivering remarkable experiences.

Nintendo was criticised for years by the so-called “specialised press” for refusing to engage in the endless battle over console power. However, the company deliberately pursued a different strategy —one that reached its peak in March 2017.

Left: Nintendo Wii U. On the right, we can see how the game *Batman: Arkham City* makes use of the console's screen controller to manage Batman's inventory and that of other controllable characters.

Nintendo Switch: the change many were perhaps waiting for

It is said that the original idea for the Nintendo Switch came from Satoru Iwata some time ago, which he proposed to Nintendo, specifically mentioning it to Tatsumi Kimishima shortly before his health deteriorated and, sadly, he passed away from the cancer that deprived all players of this remarkable mind.

According to some reports, Kimishima —Iwata's successor as president of Nintendo, who later passed the role to Shuntarō Furukawa in June 2018, shortly after Switch launched— decided to give Iwata's idea a chance, both out of respect and as a tribute to him, fulfilling his final wish, as it was his last concept for a video game console.

And so work began on the Nintendo Switch —known as “NX” until its official unveiling. Where Wii U had faltered —a system with a solid underlying concept that nevertheless failed commercially— the Switch concept surpassed it in every way. The Nintendo Switch marked a shift in Nintendo's approach, moving away from online-only gaming to embrace true, classic multiplayer: side by side, with your friends or anyone else, anywhere in the real world, both playing on the same system or with their own. This does not mean the console lacks online play entirely —services over the internet were made available later, which, like those of Sony or Microsoft consoles, also require a subscription.

Nintendo Switch represented a genuine rethink of what a console could be, evident even in its reveal trailer. The fact that the trailer featured not a single child, but people in their twenties and older, signalled that Nintendo had been considering the often-overlooked gamer who has left puberty behind: adults with work, studies, and responsibilities, yet still passionate about games and with limited time to enjoy them —a demographic for whom the Switch is perfectly suited.

The console is a home system that, when docked, provides video and audio output for a television and comes with a standard controller —by default, the Joy-Con, which can split and attach to the screen for handheld play sessions, though a more traditional Pro Controller, also produced by Nintendo, can be used.

Here is where it becomes truly interesting... Remove the “tablet” —the console’s main unit— from the dock and detach the Joy-Con controllers, attaching them to either side of the tablet’s screen, and you immediately have a portable console. It doesn’t end there. This portable configuration —always the same system with all the features available— also allows two players to each use a single Joy-Con as their own controller, each functioning autonomously. And all of this can be done wirelessly.

In other words, the Switch is a home console that becomes portable, and a portable console that becomes a home-like system, all in one —hence the name “Switch”. And if two players aren’t enough, others can join if someone else nearby has another Nintendo Switch, adding more players to the game using that person’s controllers.

This image, provided by Nintendo, showcases the many ways this console can be used: playing at home in docked mode, enjoying multiplayer on a single system in portable mode, or using it as a handheld while maintaining the feel of a home console, and more

At a time when video game companies increasingly rely on “remakes” —Nintendo included, to be frank—, and others choose to abandon their main franchises, ousting their top creators and reducing them to mere cinematic experiences for pachinko and pachislot machines —Konami’s treatment of Hideo Kojima and Koji Igarashi being prime examples—.

In the era of “DLCs everywhere”, the constant impression from companies is that it’s all about “who can outdo whom”, and the trend of releasing certain franchise games annually, flooding the market with the same franchises, leaving no time for brands to rest, evolve, innovate or improve —Ubisoft with *Assassin’s Creed* or Activision with *Call of Duty* are notable examples—. Amid all this, Nintendo —while not immune to the same faults as other companies, as discussed in previous paragraphs— demonstrated with the Switch that Iwata’s idea of “stop competing to make the most powerful console and instead think of new ways to play” is entirely feasible.

Using as a basis the concept of the Nvidia Shield tablet/console —indeed, Nvidia collaborated with Nintendo to develop the Switch and later the Switch 2— Nintendo went a step further, offering the very proposal I’ve been describing in these lines.

The mere possibility of moving away, even slightly, from the current market’s almost exclusive conception of multiplayer —each person at home, interacting virtually with strangers —or not— and enduring the insults of pre-teens via chat or microphone— is, in my opinion, truly noteworthy.

The very idea that a game on the scale of *Skyrim* could be played portably —as shown in the Switch’s presentation trailer, and later experienced on both the Switch and its successor—... The new *Zelda* titles —*Breath of the Wild* and *Tears of the Kingdom*— and their very design made one want to acquire the system from the moment they were announced.

And let hardcore *Zelda* fans rest easy, as the homages and similarities in these *Zelda* games to series such as *The Elder Scrolls*, *The Witcher*, or *Red Dead* did them no harm —we had to have faith, for is there really any *The Legend of Zelda* game that is genuinely bad, excluding *Link’s Crossbow Training*?—.

And you... what did you think of Nintendo Switch’s concept? Personally, thanks to its announcement, and after years of disenchantment as a gamer and video game researcher regarding the attitude of major companies toward users, I finally regained the desire to acquire new home consoles back then.

Sources

- **Texts consulted:** Official Nintendo website, doctoral thesis by Andrés Domenech Alcaide: *Los videojuegos como producto del Arte: La importancia del cómic, el cine, y otras artes en su historia (Video Games as Works of Art: The Importance of Comics, Cinema, and Other Arts in Their History)*, IGN, Gamespot | Text created by: Andrés Domenech Alcaide [CoolJapan.es]
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